

Data on bacterial community composition of *Bactrocera dorsalis* as affected by antibiotics and eggs disinfection

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Figure S1. Multiple samples rarefaction curves based on 16S rRNA genes pyrosequencing (A) and the species rank abundance curves (B). S1-S2-S3: Biological replicate 1, 2 and 3 of symbiotic sample; Ap1-Ap2-Ap3: Biological replicate 1, 2 and 3 of aposymbiotic sample and Ax1-Ax2-Ax3: Biological replicate 1, 2 and 3 of axenic sample.

Figure S2. Cluster heat map representing the relative abundance of 35 most dominant bacterial genera from S: Symbiotic; Ap: Aposymbiotic and Ax: Axenic ($n = 10 \times 3 = 30$) *B. dorsalis* microbiota. Colored bars represent the five indicate identified phyla (Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Cyanobacteria, Firmicutes, and Proteobacteria). Non-colored bars indicate non identified bacteria. Left heat map indicates the relative abundance of the three biological replicates from each treatment, while right heat map represents the technical replicates, both clustered as regard to their degree of similarity.

Figure S3. Petal diagram showing the shared and abundance of OTUs between replicates of all treatment groups (S: Symbiotic; Ap: Aposymbiotic and Ax: Axenic).

Table S1: Consensus lineage of core bacterial community between treatment groups (S: Symbiotic; Ap: Aposymbiotic and Ax: Axenic).

OTU_ID	Kingdom	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
OTU_1	Bacteria	Acidobacteria	Blastocatellia	unidentified	Blastocatellaceae	-	-
OTU_2	Bacteria	Acidobacteria	Blastocatellia	unidentified	Blastocatellaceae	<i>Blastocatella</i>	-
OTU_3	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	unidentified	Micrococcales	Brevibacteriaceae	<i>Brevibacterium</i>	-
OTU_4	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	unidentified	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	<i>Kocuria</i>	<i>marina</i>
OTU_5	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Rubrobacteria	Rubrobacterales	Rubrobacteriaceae	<i>Rubrobacter</i>	-
OTU_6	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Rikenellaceae	<i>Alistipes</i>	-
OTU_7	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	<i>Prevotella</i>	<i>nanceiensis</i>
OTU_8	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Sphingobacteria	Sphingobacteriales	Chitinophagaceae	-	-
OTU_9	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Prevotellaceae	<i>Alloprevotella</i>	-
OTU_10	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	<i>Porphyromonas</i>	<i>endodontalis</i>
OTU_11	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Vagococcus</i>	-
OTU_12	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Enterococcus</i>	<i>durans</i>
OTU_13	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	<i>Lactococcus</i>	<i>lactis</i>
OTU_14	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	<i>Streptococcus</i>	-
OTU_15	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Rhuminococcaceae	-	-
OTU_16	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Vagococcus</i>	<i>teuberi</i>
OTU_17	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Lactobacillaceae	<i>Lactobacillus</i>	-

OTU_18	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	<i>Lachnoclostridium</i>	<i>clostridioforme</i>
OTU_19	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Negativicutes	Selenomonadales	Veillonellaceae	<i>Veillonella</i>	-
OTU_20	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	<i>Lachnospiraceae</i>	-
OTU_21	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	<i>Eisenbergiella</i>	-
OTU_22	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	<i>Anaerostipes</i>	-
OTU_23	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Rumunococcaceae	<i>Butyrococcus</i>	-
OTU_24	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Vagococcus</i>	<i>teuberi</i>
OTU_25	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Rumunococcaceae	<i>Flavonifractor</i>	-
OTU_26	Bacteria	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	<i>Fusobacterium</i>	<i>periodonticum</i>
OTU_27	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>aeruginosa</i>
OTU_28	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Morganella</i>	-
OTU_29	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	<i>Ralstonia</i>	<i>solanacearum</i>
OTU_30	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	<i>Acinetobacter</i>	-
OTU_31	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterococcaceae	<i>Escherichia-Shigella</i>	-
OTU_32	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	<i>Enterobacter</i>	-
OTU_33	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	<i>Providencia</i>	-
OTU_34	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	<i>Proteus</i>	<i>mirabilis</i>
OTU_35	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Orbales	Orbaceae	<i>Orbus</i>	-
OTU_36	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Neisseriales	Neisseriaceae	<i>Neisseria</i>	<i>oralis</i>
OTU_37	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Orbales	Orbaceae	<i>Orbus</i>	<i>cronobacter</i>

OTU_38	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Caulobacterales	Caulobacteraceae	<i>Brevundimonas</i>	<i>dimunita</i>
OTU_39	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Desulfovibrionales	Desulfovibrionaceae	<i>Desulfovibrio</i>	<i>putealis</i>
OTU_40	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Alcaligenaceae	<i>Achromobacter</i>	-
OTU_42	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	-
OTU_43	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	<i>Serratia</i>	<i>marcescens</i>
OTU_44	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	-	-
OTU_45	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteriaceae	<i>Paracoccus</i>	-
OTU_46	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	<i>Moraxella</i>	<i>lacunata</i>
OTU_47	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Epsilonproteobacteria	Campylobacterales	Campylobacteriaceae	<i>Campylobacter</i>	<i>gracilis</i>

Table S2: Nutrient composition of the experimental diets [1, 2]

Ingredients	Components	Contents (mg)	
		F	NE
Essential amino acids	L-arginine	50.45	
	L-histidine	21.54	
	L-isoleucine	26.64	
	L-leucine	51.02	
	L-lysine	27.78	
	L-methionine	13.04	
	L-phenylalanine	33.44	
	L-threonine	25.51	
	L-tryptophan	13.60	
	L-valine	37.41	
Non-essential amino acids	L-alanine	36.85	36.85
	L-aspartic acid	53.28	53.28
	L-cysteine	19.27	19.27
	L-glutamic acid	185.36	185.36
	Glycine	42.51	42.51
	L-proline	58.95	58.95
	L-serine	36.85	36.85
	L-tyrosine	22.67	22.67
Minerals and salts	FeSO ₄	2.50	2.50
	MnSO ₄	0.63	0.63
	ZnCl ₂	0.63	0.63
	CuSO ₄	0.31	0.31
	MgSO ₄	20.00	20.00
	KH ₂ PO ₄	84.65	84.65
	Ca(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂	10.00	10.00
	KCl	117.00	117.00
	NaCl	45.00	45.00
White sugar	10000.0	10000.0	
DDW	50000.00	50000.00	

F: Full diet; NE: Non-essential amino acid diets; DDW: Deionized distilled water.

Validation of egg sterility

The axenic state of disinfected embryos was validated by PCR of variable regions V1-3 of the 16S rRNA gene using universal primers (27F/1459R) and cultivable technique using dilution plating of eggs homogenate on agar plate-medium, respectively. Twenty surface sterilized eggs (out of the 50 earlier sterilized) and twenty untreated eggs (collected from the lab colony) were used and subdivided in two groups of ten eggs each: egg samples from one group were used for dilution plating on agar plate-media while those from the second group were used for DNA extraction (CTAB/SDS method) [3]. Eggs from each group were separately and individually crushed in Eppendorf tubes containing 500 μ L of PBS solution. Homogenized guts from one group were serially diluted by 10^{-4} – 10^{-8} , 50 μ L of which were plated onto Luria Bertani (LB) agar media and incubated at 30°C for 24–48 h, while those from the second group were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min and the pellets were used for DNA extraction and polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The PCR reactions were performed in a programmed thermal cycler under the following conditions: Initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min, followed by 30 cycles at 94°C for 1 min, annealing at 53°C, 54°C, 55°C or 58 °C for 1 min 30 sec, 72°C for 1 min and a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. Any surface sterilized eggs homogenate growing on agar medium or PCR bands were visible were discarded and the egg sterilization process was repeated until no bacterial colonies or DNA bands were seen.

Absolute gut bacterial abundance by qPCR

An estimation of the sizes of gut microbial communities showed a content of $10.77 \times 10^7 \pm 2.21 \times 10^7$ Reads per gut of symbiotic flies, which was significantly higher than

those detected in aposymbiotic and axenic flies ($2.82 \times 10^7 \pm 1.04 \times 10^6$ and $1.71 \times 10^7 \pm 7.59 \times 10^6$, respectively) (ANOVA, $df = 2$; $F = 111.351$; $P < 0.0001$ and $df = 2$; $F = 111.351$; $P < 0.0001$, respectively). However, there was no difference of gut microbial contents between the aposymbiotic and axenic flies (Chi square, $\chi^2 = 9.73$, $R^2 = 0.978$, $P = 0.699$).

Figure S4. Gut symbiont contents estimated by qPCR using universal primers against 16S rDNA. There was no statistical difference between aposymbiotic and axenic treatments ($P > 0.05$), and both were highly different from the symbiotic one with similar p values ($P < 0.001$).

Figure S5. Family abundance of bacterial community composition as revealed by 454-pyrosequencing. S: Symbiotic; Ap: Aposymbiotic and Ax: Axenic

Figure S6. Bacterial composition at species level (A): Gut bacterial species composition and (B): Ternary phase diagram. The three vertices in the figure (B) represent the three sample groups. The circle represents the species. The circle size is proportional to the relative abundance. The closer the circle is to the vertex, the higher the content of this species in this group. S: symbiotic; Ap: aposymbiotic and Ax: axenic

References

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3. William S, Feil H, Copeland A, 2012. Bacterial genomic DNA isolation using CTAB. *Sigma*, 50(6876).